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PROTEOMIC STUDIES OF CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS OF *COMMELINA COMMUNIS*

Nagavalli Dhandapani*, Saranya Sundaralingama, Anu Baskaranb, Aruna Muthusamyb Brindha Vasudevanb, Dhivya Muruganb, Divya Gopalakrishnanb, Sujarithajayarajb

Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Adhiparasakthi College of Pharmacy, Melmaruvathur.

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ABSTRACT

The present research work was aimed to discover anti-viral and anti-dengue activity of the phytochemical constituents present in *Commelina communis* using Molecular docking studies. In this research work, we have screened 10 chemical constituents from *Commelina communis* through docking studies, in an effort to develop novel anti-dengue and anti-viral activity, the target enzymes were chosen for the study is 4M9K, 3P54, 2V33, 5FC8 and 5B1C using Argus lab 4.0.1 software. Among the 10 screened compounds of *Commelina communis*, shows best to moderate (-9.49194kcal/mol to -5.61913kcal/mol) binding energy and various bonding interactions against the targeted proteins. On the basis of docking study results, it can be concluded that chemical constituents of *Commelina communis*, serve as promising chemical probes to design therapeutic agents with anti-dengue, and antiviral properties.

Corresponding author

Nagavalli Dhandapani

Professor and Head,
Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry,
Adhiparasakthi College of Pharmacy,
Melmaruvathur.

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INTRODUCTION

Dengue fever (DF) and dengue hemorrhagic fever (DHF) are acute febrile diseases transmitted by mosquitoes. Nowadays, they are the most rapidly spreading mosquito-borne diseases in the world. In recent decades, these diseases have spread to over more than 100 countries. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that the year 2016 was characterized by large dengue outbreaks worldwide. The Region of the Americas region reported more than 2.38 million cases in 2016, where Brazil alone contributed slightly less than 1.5 million cases, approximately 3 times higher than in 2014.

The disease has four viral serotypes (DENV 1–4), and its spectrum ranges from asymptomatic infection to dengue fever (DF), dengue hemorrhagic fever (DHF), and dengue shock syndrome (DSS), and may lead to patient death, all four serotypes of dengue virus are transmitted to humans by the *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus* mosquitoes.^[1] The global burden of viral disease is very high and set against a backdrop of increasing antimicrobial resistance. There is an urgent need for alternatives to anti-viral that are effective and less likely to lead to drug resistance. Viruses consist of a genome and sometimes a few enzymes stored in a capsule made of protein (called a capsid), and sometimes covered with a lipid layer (called an 'envelope'). Viruses cannot reproduce own, and instead propagate by subjugating a host cell to produce copies of them, thus producing the next generation.^[2]

Antiviral drugs are one class of antimicrobials, a larger group which also includes antibiotic (also termed antibacterial), anti-dengue, antifungal and anti-parasitic drugs or antiviral drugs based on monoclonal antibodies.^[3] Most antivirals are considered relatively harmless to the host, and therefore can be used to treat infections. They should be distinguished from viricides, which are not medication but deactivate or destroy virus particles, either inside or outside the body. Plants are an important source of antiviral compounds and traditional healers have long used plants to prevent or cure infectious diseases. There is a recent renewed interest into the use of natural products for the identification of new members of the 'antibiotic-ome' (defined as natural products with antibiotic activity), and their application in antiviral drug discovery in the genomics era.^[4] Phytochemicals are the active biological component of plants like *Andrographis paniculata* (nila vembu), *Carica papaya* (papaya), *Azadirachta indica* (neem), *Solanum trilobatum* (Tuduvalai), *Allium cepa* (Vengayam) and some phytochemicals including tannins, alkaloids, terpenoids and flavonoids possess antiviral activity.^[5]

Researchers working on such "rational drug design" strategies for developing antivirals have tried to attack viruses at every stage of their life cycles. *Commelina communis* have been found to contain multiple antiviral chemicals with similar synergistic effects. Our data provides a strong case for pursuing liposome-based, toxin-sequestering therapy for use as a clinical treatment for life-threatening viral infections. The study reported here in concerns our efforts to optimize chemical components of *Commelina communis* against viral target proteins with best anti-viral and anti-dengue activity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preparation of protein structure

The 3D structure of 3P54 (Crystal Structure of the Japanese Encephalitis Virus Envelope Protein, strain SA-14-14-2)^[6], 2V33 (High resolution crystal structure of domain III of E1 fusion glycoprotein of Semliki Forest Virus)^[7], 5B1C (Crystal structure of DEN4 ED3 mutant with L387I)^[8], 4M9K (NS2B-NS3 protease from dengue virus at pH 5.5)^[9] and 5FC8 (Mouse importin alpha: Dengue 3 NS5 C-terminal NLS peptide complex)^[10] viral and dengue proteins are used for the current study. The protein sequence was retrieved in the fasta format and the 3D structure was determined using CPH model server. All water molecules were removed and hydrogen atoms were added to the target protein molecule.

Preparation of the ligand structures

The ligands used for docking study were selected from the literature. The bioactive compounds those are mainly present in the *Commelina communis* under Plantae Kingdom, Commelinaceae Family and *Commelina* Genus *communis* Species, commonly known as the Asiatic dayflower were considered for the study. The ligand structures were generated using the tool Chemskech. Three-dimensional optimizations of the ligand structures were done and saved as '.mol file'. Geometry optimizations of the ligands were performed according to the Hartree-Fock (HF) calculation method using ArgusLab 4.0.1 (Mark A. Thompson, Planaria Software LLC, Seattle, WA, USA, <http://www.arguslab.com>)^[11] software. The compounds included in the study are luteolin-7-O-beta-D-glucoside, azelaic acid, vanillic acid, thymine, syringic acid, uracil, vitexin, luteolin-6-C-beta-D-glucoside, protocatechuic acid, benzoic acid, Beta-sitosterol and rutin^[12] respectively. The bioactive compounds considered for the study are listed in figure: 7.

Azelaic acid

Vanillic acid

Thymine

Luteolin-7-O-beta-D-glucoside

Syringic acid

Luteolin-6-C-glucoside

Uracil

Vitexin

Protocatechuic acid

Benzoic acid

Beta-Sitosterol

Rutin

Fig: 7 Chemical constituent of *Commelina communis* and their structures.

Binding site prediction

Q-Site Finder^[13] (<http://www.bioinformatics.leeds.ac.uk/qsitefinder>) and PDB sum^[14] (<http://www.biochem.ucl.ac.uk/bsm/pdbsum>). are used for binding site prediction. It uses the interaction energy between the protein and a simple van der Waals probe to locate energetically favourable binding sites.

Protein-ligand docking using ArgusLab 4.0.1

ArgusLab is an electronic structure program that is based on the quantum mechanics. It predicts the potential energies, molecular structures; geometry optimization of structure, vibration frequencies of coordinates of atoms, bond length, and bond angle.

4M9K, 3P54, 2V33, 5FC8 and 5B1C protein was docked individually against the each bioactive compound from the leaves of *Commelina communis* using ArgusLab^[9]. The interaction was carried out to find the favourable binding geometries of the ligand with the protein. Docking of the protein ligand complex was mainly targeted only to the predicted active site. Docking simulations were performed by selecting “ArgusDock” as the docking engine. The selected residues of the receptor were defined to be a part of the binding site. A spacing of 0.4 Å between the grid points was used and an exhaustive search was performed by enabling “High precision” option in Docking precision menu, “Dock” was chosen as the calculation type, “flexible” for the ligand, and the “AScore” was used as the scoring function. A maximum of 150 poses were allowed to be analyzed; binding site box size was set to 20 × 20 × 20 Å so as to encompass the entire active site. The AScore function, with the parameters read from the AScore.prm file, was used to calculate the binding energies of the resulting docked structures^[15]. All the compounds in the dataset were docked into the active site of the selected protein, using the same protocol. The docking poses saved for each compound were ranked according to their dock score function. The pose having the highest dock score was selected for further analysis^[11].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The ligand was docked with the target proteins, and the best docking poses were identified. A figure: 7 shows the structures of ligands. Figures: 2–6 shows the binding poses of the azelaic acid. This best docking poses shows how the ligand molecule fits into the binding region of the target protein. Intermolecular flexible docking simulations were performed and energy values were calculated from the docked conformations of the 4M9K, 3P54, 2V33, 5FC8 and 5B1C anti-viral and anti-dengue protein–inhibitor complexes. Majority of the ligands had a greater binding affinity with the targeted anti-viral and anti-dengue protein. Inhibition was measured by the binding energy of the best ligand pose measured in kcal/mol. The binding pose and their energy are listed in Table 1.

Figure: 2 Binding pose of azelaic acid with 4M9K.

Figure: 3 Binding pose of azelaic acid with 3P54.

Figure: 4 Binding pose of azelaic acid with 2V33.

Figure: 5 Binding pose of azelaic acid with 5FC8.

Figure: 6 Binding pose of azelaic acid with 5B1C.

Table: 1 Phyto constituents with docking energy.

S.NO	NAME OF THE COMPOUNDS	BINDING POSE WITH DOCKING ENERGY kcal/mol				
		PROTEINS				
		4M9K	3P54	2V33	5FC8	5B1C
1.	Vanillic acid	-6.7155	-6.7979	-7.0497	-7.1531	-7.9664
2.	Luteolin 6 –C-beta-D-glucoside	-6.8012	-6.7617	-7.1393	-6.8185	-6.9413
3.	Luteolin-7-O-beta-D-glucoside	-7.5017	-7.1264	-7.9139	-7.8302	-7.3406
4.	Azelaic acid	-9.4919	-9.2910	-7.9328	-8.0476	-9.2874
5.	Protocatecuic acid	-7.9397	-7.3633	-6.5757	-6.8870	-7.2705
6.	Vitexin	-4.8616	-5.9392	-5.6191	-5.0908	-5.2970
7.	Syringic acid	-7.1534	-8.0205	-7.1100	-7.3643	-7.8809
8.	Thymine	-5.5994	-5.60235	-5.4265	-5.5060	-5.6432
9.	Benzoic acid	No ligand pose	-	-	-	-
10.	Uracil	No ligand pose	-	-	-	-
11.	Rutin	No ligand pose	-	-	-	-
12.	Beta-sitosterol	No ligand pose	-	-	-	-

CONCLUSION

All the compounds selected for the study are considered as orally safe compounds. A few compounds showed interaction with the selected anti-viral and anti-dengue protein. A few compounds were not able to interact with the target protein. Thus the bioactive compounds that are interacting with the target can be used as a potent inhibitor to block the action of 4M9K, 3P54, 2V33, 5FC8 and 5B1C anti-viral and anti-dengue protein. Thus the selected compounds can be verified at the clinical-level drug examinations and made into an effective anti-viral and anti-dengue drug.

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